

Pena : A cultural bridge in the Meitei Community's music, heritage and society

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Abstract

This research paper is an analytical study of the relation and the role of Pena to the society and their culture of the Meitei community. Pena is an indigenous musical instrument of Manipur and has been an inseparable part of their life and culture. Musical Instrument and their story have always been a part of the history of Manipur. Pena, being a folk musical instrument, it play an important role in the society of meitei community. It holds an important position in the folk music of Manipur. It is a central part of the folk music of Manipur. The main objective of this research paper is to preserve, promote and to analyze the importance of Pena ethnographically. The method which is going to be used in this research paper are documentation, descriptive method personal interview, audio video recording, observation, data collection of related printed books etc. The findings of this research paper will explore the emotions of the people of meitei community towards Pena and the significant of Pena in their society.

Key Words : Pena, folk instrument, Meitei community, Manipur culture, Lai Haraoba, Yakairol

Research Paper

Introduction

This research paper is an analytical study of the relation and the role of Pena to the society and their culture of the Meitei community. Pena is an indigenous musical instrument of Manipur and has been an inseparable part of their life and culture. Musical instrument and their story have always been a part of the history of Manipur.

'Kangleipak' at present known as Manipur is a small beautiful state situated at North eastern part of India. It is a land of Festival. 'Music and dance' are the integral part of the religious and social life of the people of Manipur. Meitei is the majority indigenous ethnic community among the 33 communities. Music is an inseparable part of their culture and heritage, it reflect the history, values and experiences of the community. They express their unique stories and perspectives preserving their cultural heritage for future generation through music. It creates a sense of belonging and unity among the individuals of this ethnic community."(Dimbajit 1)

"In Meitei society music is ever-present in the daily life of each individual, it is like impossible to imagine their life without music and dance. In their society music accompany every activity of human from the cradle

to grave including lullabies, dancing, rites, battles and games and ceremonies like weddings, marriage, funerals and entertainment. We can also say that they express their life in all aspects through the medium of music."(Manihar Singh 12)

Few songs I would like to mention which they sung in their day to day life:

Lullaby

They sing lullaby, they called it as 'Naosum esei' in their dialect. It is a cradle song which is one of the most universal form of music. The mother sing this form of music to induce her infant to sleep. We can also this as the first communication to an infant. Meitei community sung this traditionally since time immemorial. The title of this Naosum esei is 'Tha tha Thabung ton'.

Games

In games the children have sung many songs. For example:

- 'Oo Laobi'
- 'Sey sey seboti'
- 'Kwak tanba'
- 'Tong Tong tongdrungbi' etc.

Research Problem

Due to globalisation the world is changing and developing so fast. In this modern world it become a challenge to preserve the folk music and folk musical instrument which have less vocabulary. Preserving folk music is very must need in order to preserve the cultural heritage of a community. Cultural preservation is the essential concept which safeguard the heritage of the society. It is important because music also play a vital role in peace building of a society, we can also used it as a psychological tool to reduce stress and anxiety. So it is really needed to be preserved.

Objective

The key motive for conducting this study is to bring the importance of pena in the limelight so that people from the rest of the world come to know about Pena of the Meitei community. And to preserve, promote and highlight the importance of "Pena", Manipuri folk instrument among the people, for the welfare of the society.

PENA

"Not only the singing, musical instrument like Pena also play a central part of the cultural heritage of the Meitei community. Pena is a very old folk musical string (Bow) instrument, being a folk musical instrument it play an important role in the society of Manipur. It holds an important position in the folk music of Manipur. It is the central part of the folk music of Manipur."(Achoubisan). This melodic folk spike fiddle was also recognised as royal court music in Kings' time. Pena music has different composition to express different emotion. Some compositions are:

1. "Hepli-pabot : This is connected with the mood and the atmosphere of courage.
2. Shikaplon : This is connected to the expressing mood of moaning.
3. Leimaron Sheiron : This is connected to expressing joy and describing beauty.
4. Panthoibi Sheiron : This is connected to prayers." (Premchand53)

Pena in the Royal Court

According to the Royal Chronicle, Pena is associated with the royal court. Pena singer sings early in the morning to evoked the King sleeps. Pena Music composition like 'Yaikairol' is used in it. And the it is not same for every king, composition like Lam-een was sung when the king start a journey for a tour.

Pena in Lai Haraoba

Lai Haraoba is the primary and most important ritual performance of Meitei. "T.C. Hudson the writer of the book called 'The Meithei' has expressed almost the same opinion. He, however, prefers Lai Haraoba to mean 'rejoicing of gods'. A local Manipuri scholar, Mr. E. Nilakanta Singh has used the word to mean 'merry-making of the God and Goddesses' " (Premchand 37). This ritual performance is celebrated about 7 to 15 days. It is decided by the maibas and pandits. "These rituals performance is always conducted with the help of three ritual functionaries called Maibi, Maiba and Pena khongba. Pena khongba is an artist who play Pena, an old indigenous musical instrument. He is not merely an instrumentalist but a singer and dancer also. He play a significant role throughout the duration of this ritual performance. He provide musical accompaniment to most of the ritual sequence and sing song prescribe for the particular sequence. For example in Lai Haraoba everyday in the morning the Pena khongba sits in front of the two deities and sing Yaikairol, a song of inviting the deities to the day's programmes. Again in the end of the Lai Haraoba performance the Pena khongba will sing 'Nongkarol' song by which the deities involved in the performance leave the venue. " (Premchand 52).

Pena in Religious Ceremonies

1. Use of Pena in the birth rite

"Pena were used in the birth rite of a baby, In this ceremony, the Pena usually sing the Thawai Mikourol. Both the parents, and the baby are made to listen to the song sung describing the Pagi-param pugi param (patriliny) of the newborn. To be blessed with long life,

after singing the song, boons are prayed from the Pena maestro. The utility of the Pena at birth that was once a glorious ingredient of the Manipuri culture has now become faint due to the changes bring by this modern world." (Mongsaba 99)

Pena in Wedding

Pena music were sing and play as a way of prayer and worship. Some example of Pena music sung in the wedding are 'Nongkhong Koyba', 'Panthoibi Khonggul' etc. An episode of the song that sung at the wedding is given below:

An episode of wedding song lyrics:

Sonnapungi mayaida, neengthijare fajare

Lainingthouna yetta fam, Lairembina oida Ngalle.

Lainingthounasu hende, Lairembinasu Watte.Fajareda

Iningthou, sanagi tangbal mathakta Sajik ani thokkumle,

thaba ani ngangumle. Lainingthougi kokthakta sanagi

Kokyetna Nganthoire. Lairembigi kokthakta Kajengleina

Nganthoire. Fajare Lainingthou, fajare Lairembi.

Panthouna yomba khayomni, Palemna punba leipunni.

Yengu yengu anise, pakhang nura anise, kanana Watliba

kanana helliba anise, fajabada Hainingai leite,

yengbada pukning nung-olli. Atiya da thokpa thajana

ngasi malemda ngallare Kanana helliba yengbada

pukning nung olle. Fajabada Hayningai leitare.Thabu

Ngamjabi maithongni'(Mongsaba103)

Pena as an entertainment music (Phamsak)

"Pena music were also used in the form of an entertainment music. Pena phamsak was a common form of entertainment. It is sung by the Pena player to entertain the people, It used to be quite popular before the British period. It was organised in the place of rich people and noblemen who have enough space on veranda or courtyard. The programme of Pena phamsak start in the evening when the people return back home from work. It is organised by the locality and community together. And it was listen till late night during the wealthy season. The Pena singer are so busy from one to two month because every locality organised this phamsak programme, so the artist were booked. They don't even return home due to these programmes. They were also offered the best dishes by the organiser in order make them feel homely. The singer different lyrics every time. Khamba Thoibi and other legendary stories were sung by the Pena players." (Harimati Devi 47)

Impact of the ongoing conflict of Manipur on Pena Music

It become a difficult period for the people of Manipur to live with peace and harmony. This conflict had an impact on the music and culture of the Manipur. More than 33 temple and around 44 Umang Laiharaopham (place where Lai haraoba is performed) were destroyed and burnt down where people used to perform the ritual performance where Pena has been as an inseparable part of the performance. Due to the unrest, the people, the artist could not perform, instead people are trying to save their live. It gave a negative impact to the culture and heritage of the Manipur which affect in the development of the music in Manipur.

Research Methodology

In this research paper I have used methods like descriptive method, Observation, Data collection of related printed books, Manuscript, Photograph and oral literature, Interview etc.

Conclusion

In this research paper I have discussed the uses, the functions of Pena music in meitei community, I have shown the importance of Pena in the culture and society of Manipur. My research paper will help in study musicology to the upcoming generation and it will also help the society in shaping and defining their identity, culture and traditions. It will serves as an educational tool for passing down traditional values and knowledge.

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